

STUDY ON AXIAL COMPRESSION PERFORMANCE OF FRP BARS REINFORCED SEA-SAND CONCRETE ENCASED SQUARE STEEL TUBE COLUMNS

Zhiqiang Dong, Southeast University, China, zhiqiang.dong@seu.edu.cn
Tianhao Han, Southeast University, China, 230218119@seu.edu.cn
Pengfei Yue, Nanjing Forestry University, China, 424389137@qq.com
Hong Zhu, Southeast University, China, alice_zhuhong@seu.edu.cn
Yang Wei, Nanjing Forestry University, China, wy78@njfu.edu.cn

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a novel sea-sand concrete column that was hybrid reinforced with fiber-reinforced-polymer (FRP) bars and steel tubes is proposed. Among them, the steel tube was filled with ordinary concrete inside, and the sea-sand concrete was used outside with the reinforcement of FRP bars. To avoid corrosion of the steel tube, FRP sheets were wrapped outside the steel tube to isolate it from the chloride ions in the sea sand. The test parameters include the existing of steel tubes, different side lengths of steel tubes, thicknesses of steel tubes. Through the axial compression test, the compressive performances of the hybrid reinforced columns were tested. The results showed that the decreasing of FRP stirrup spacings and the increasing thickness of steel tube greatly enhanced the compressive bearing capacity of the test column. The positive effect of varying the side lengths of the steel tube was not obvious, even if the side length is doubled.

KEYWORDS

FRP bars; Seawater sea-sand concrete; Steel tube; Axial compression; Columns

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of infrastructure projects, the demand for concrete has surged. The use of river sand and fresh water, which are widely used as raw materials in traditional concrete, has also increased dramatically. This has led to more and more rampant sand mining and digging, which not only affects the water environment but also causes various disasters. Therefore, it is urgent to find other materials that can replace fresh water and river sand (Xiao, Qiang, Nanni, & Zhang, 2017; Zhao, Hu, Shi, Zhang, & Zhu, 2021). In recent years, seawater and sea sand concrete made by replacing fresh water and river sand with seawater and sea sand has gradually attracted researchers' interests. Its rational development and utilization can not only alleviate the overuse of river sand and fresh water resources, but also can save transportation costs, reduce engineering costs, and have significant economic and social benefits for marine engineering and coastal city construction (Dong, Wu, Zhao, Zhu, & Lian, 2018; Y. Li, Teng, Zhao, & Raman, 2018; Zeng, Duan, Gao, Bai, & Ouyang, 2020). Relevant research shows that seawater sea sand concrete has similar mechanical properties to ordinary concrete, so it can be applied in project engineering (M. Guo et al., 2020; X. Guo, Xiong, Jin, & Pang, 2022; P. Li, Li, Yu, Qu, & Tam, 2020). However, the high content of corrosive ions such as chloride ions in seawater sea is a problem that hinders the large-scale application of seawater sea sand concrete in actual projects (Ahmed, Guo, Zhang, Shi, & Zhu, 2020).

In recent years, fiber-reinforced composite materials (FRP) have been increasingly used in constructions due to their high strength-to-weight ratio and good corrosion resistance (Cadenazzi, Nolan, Mazzocchi, Stringer, & Nanni, 2020; Dong et al., 2020). Existing research shows that the performance of FRP bars is less affected by environments with high levels of corrosive ions such as chloride ions, so FRP bars can be combined with seawater sea sand concrete (Xie et al., 2022; K. Zhang, Zhang, & Xiao, 2022). The combination of FRP bars and seawater sea sand concrete can replace most of the ordinary steel bars and ordinary concrete used in marine engineering, effectively

reducing the amount of ordinary concrete used, thereby saving water resources and river sand resources (Hu, Xiao, Zhang, & Zhang, 2022; Z. Xiong, Zeng, Li, Kwan, & He, 2021).

The form of concrete filled steel tubes is composed of external steel tubes and internal core concrete, which can fully exert their advantages and overcome their respective shortcomings (Dundu, 2012; Ekmekyapar & Al-Eliwi, 2016; Lai & Ho, 2016; Schneider Stephen, 1998). Since the lateral deformation coefficient of the steel tube is smaller than concrete, it can confine the lateral expansion of inner concrete during the application of axial load, improving the strength and deformation ability of the concrete. On the other hand, the inner concrete can also support the steel tube, which can fully exert the characteristics of high strength and high bearing capacity of steel. Due to its excellent performance, concrete-filled steel tube columns have become a hot research topic (An & Han, 2014; Lee, Uy, Kim, Choi, & Choi, 2011; Zeng, Zheng, Liu, Guo, & Hou, 2021). The previous research mainly uses different diameter-thickness ratios and section shapes of steel tubes, loading methods, concrete strength grades, concrete types etc. as variables to conduct a series of experimental researches and numerical analyses on concrete-filled steel tube columns, and proposed a more concise and reliable bearing capacity calculation formula (Han & An, 2014; Hou & Zhou, 2022; Lai & Ho, 2017; Nguyen, Thai, Ngo, Uy, & Li, 2021).

Against on the above background, this paper proposes a composite structure of FRP bars reinforced sea-sand concrete encased square steel tube columns. In this composite form, FRP bars are used to reinforce seawater sea sand concrete, and steel tubes wrapped with FRP sheet are set inside it. The wrapping of FRP can effectively solve the problem of chloride ion corrosion on the steel tube in seawater sea sand concrete. In order to prevent internal buckling of steel tubes, ordinary concrete is poured inside steel tubes. This article explores the bearing capacity of this composite structure through axial compression tests, and investigates the effects of three test variables: the existing of steel tubes; different side lengths of steel tubes; thicknesses of steel tubes, which can provide a foundation for future researches on this type of structure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Design of specimens

In this study, 12 hybrid columns were cast and tested under axial compression, and these columns were 250 mm in diameter and 750 mm in height. The test parameters included the side lengths of steel tubes (60 mm or 120 mm), the thickness of steel tubes (2.5mm or 5 mm), and the FRP stirrup spacing (50 mm, 70mm or 100mm). The columns were classified into different categories based on the test variables for easy recognition, as shown in **Table 1**. The terms “AL1” and “AL2” refer to the 120 mm diameter of steel tubes and the 60 mm diameter of steel tubes, respectively. “T2.5” and “T5” refer to the thickness of steel tubes of 2.5 mm and 5 mm, respectively. Three FRP stirrup spacings were considered in this study, and “50”, “70” and “100” designated FRP stirrup spacings of 50 mm, 70 mm and 100 mm. For example, “AL1T2.5-70” means the column is reinforced by the steel tube with 120 mm in side length and 2.5 mm in thickness, and the FRP stirrup spacing is 70 mm. The cross section of specimens is shown in **Figure 1**.

Table 1. Specific details of the specimens.

Specimen	Height (mm)	Side length (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Number of steel tube	FRP stirrup spacings (mm)
AL1T2.5-50	750	120	2.5	1	50
AL1T2.5-70	750	120	2.5	1	70
AL1T2.5-100	750	120	2.5	1	100
AL1T5-50	750	120	5	1	50
AL1T5-70	750	120	5	1	70
AL1T5-100	750	120	5	1	100
AL2T2.5-50	750	60	2.5	1	50
AL2T2.5-70	750	60	2.5	1	70
AL2T2.5-100	750	60	2.5	1	100
AL0T2.5-50	750	N.A	N.A	N.A	50
AL0T2.5-70	750	N.A	N.A	N.A	70
AL0T2.5-100	750	N.A	N.A	N.A	100

Figure 1: The cross section of specimens.

Preparation of specimens and materials

Two types of steel tubes were supplied by the Nanjing local company, and the specific details can be found in **Table 1**. As shown in **Figure 2(b)**, two different side lengths of square steel tube were utilized as the inner filler, and BFRP sheets were wrapped around them to ensure the durability and bearing capacity. One note that the surface of square steel tube was polished to keep the bonding effect between FRP and steel tube (**Figure 2(a)**). After that, C30 concrete was prepared on-site and poured into steel tubes, that formed concrete filled steel tube structures. Detailed C30 concrete mixture proportions are listed in **Table 2**. The prepared specimens can be seen in Fig., and the arrangement of strain gauges is also shown. Due to the excellent corrosion resistance, basalt fiber-reinforced-polymer (BFRP) bars were chosen as the reinforcement for seawater sea sand concrete, which came from Nanjing Green Valley Material company. **Figure 2(c)** shows the reinforcement framework of BFRP bars and the position of strain gauges.

12 square wooden models with 750 mm in height and 250 mm in side length were prepared to produce the composite columns. Meanwhile, the concrete filled steel tube structures were fixed in the center of wooden models, and the reinforcement of BFRP bars was also placed for the next procedure of pouring seawater sea sand concrete. Due to the high transportation cost of seawater, chemical reagents were used to prepare seawater, and seawater is configured according to the following mix ratio. Sea sand was a mixture of medium sand and fine sand, the ratio is as follows. After the preparation of sea water and seasand, C30 sea water seasand concrete was casted into the wooden models and the detailed mix portion can be seen in **Table 2**. The wooden models were taken off after

28-day standard curing, and the relative fabrication process of composite columns were shown in Figure 2.

Table 2. The mixing proportions of concrete.

Types of concrete	Strength grade	Water cement ratio	Sea water (kg/m ³)	Cement (kg/m ³)	Sea sand (kg/m ³)	Corase aggragates (kg/m ³)
Seawater sea sand concrete	C30	0.49	214	440	605	1141
Normal concrete	C30	0.40	175	461	512	1252

Figure 2: Fabrication process of specimens.

Test instrumentations and procedures

The loading device used in this study is a 5000kN compression testing machine, and a TDS530 data acquisition instrument was used to collect test load, strain, and displacement data. Loading process was controlled by displacement at a rate of 0.5mm/min (Y. Zhang, Wei, Bai, Wu, & Dong, 2020). High-strength gypsum was applied to both ends of the specimens to ensure uniform distribution of the axial load. According to one theory, gypsum is necessary to provide enough liquid to level the bearing surface before loading. Additionally, the gypsum must be allowed to harden briefly before testing so that it can support a specific axial load (Zeng et al., 2021). Two circumferential and two longitudinal strain gauges were arranged along the circumference at the middle section of the steel tube. Meanwhile, two longitudinal strain gauges were attached to each side of the longitudinal FRP bars, and another two transverse strain gauges were attached to each side of the hoop FRP bars. Four linear variable displacement transducers (LVDTs) were located around each specimen at equal intervals to

measure the total axial displacements. **Figure 3** displays details of the experimental setup and test apparatus, while **Figure 3** also depicts the position of LVDTs.

Figure 3: Test setup of axial compression test.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Failure modes

Figure 4 shows the failure modes of specimens with different FRP stirrup spacings. Due to the multiple experimental variables, various test phenomena can be observed. During the loading process, the cracks appeared on the surface of all composite columns, and some breaking sounds of FRP bars can be heard. Therefore, the crack of seawater sea sand concrete and the fracture of partial FRP bars dominated the failure mode of all specimens. Since the mechanical properties of FRP bars and seawater sea sand concrete, specimens showed the brittle failure pattern. With the decreasing FRP stirrup spacings, more minor cracks occurred on the specimens, especially shown in **Figure 4(b)(c)**. Meanwhile, the specimens reinforced with narrow FRP stirrups showed better integrity than other specimens, consistent with previous studies (Zhe Xiong et al., 2022). As a consequence, the decreasing FRP stirrup spacings can effectively improve the integrity of specimens and reduce their damage after loading. However, compared to FRP bars reinforced seawater sea sand columns, the existing of concrete filled steel tube structure can slightly decrease the lateral expansion of specimens, attributed its remarkable bearing capacity. As shown in **Figure 4(b)(c)**, the smaller side length of steel tube can lead to the more sever failure mode of specimens, which means increasing the cross sectional area of concrete filled steel tube also can reduce the cracks of specimens. Different from these two experimental variables, the thickness of steel tube displays minor effect on the failure mode of specimens. One possible reason is the thicker steel tube can mainly improve the confinement effect on inner concrete, which is hardly found the difference from the external seawater sea sand concrete.

Figure 4: The failure mode of specimens.

Strength-strain behaviour

To simplify the discussion, the strength-strain curves in **Figure 5** were grouped according to the types of steel tube. The vertical axis for axial strength was kept at the same scale range to accurately compare the positive effects of steel tube. Based on a previous paper (Ozbakkaloglu & Lim, 2013; Vincent & Ozbakkaloglu, 2013), the strength-strain behavior of specimens was described using overall axial strains. The overall displacements were averaged by two LVDTs, and the calculation of average overall displacements divided by the height of the specimens was referred to as overall axial

strains. Axial strength was determined by dividing the axial load by the cross-sectional area of specimens, and the axial load can be measured by a compression machine.

The axial strength-axial strain curves of the specimens can be divided into three periods: a linear ascending period, a non-linear ascending period, and a non-linear descending period. In the first period, specimens showed almost the same slopes in this part, indicating that the lateral expansion of concrete columns was the main cause and these three experimental variables exhibited minor effects. The axial strength-axial strain curves showed different slopes and lasting time in the non-linear period, which means the effects of different variables were activated in this period. With the decreasing of FRP stirrup spacings, a longer lasting time and steeper slope of non-linear ascending stage can be seen from the Fig, indicating the reinforcement effect of FRP bars. This phenomenon also testified the relative failure mode in the above section, and the reinforcement of FRP bars can improve the mechanical properties of sea water seasand concrete. Compared to **Figure 5(a)**, the specimens with concrete-filled steel tube form exhibited an obvious improvement in this part, that testified the excellent bearing capacity of this form can enhance the peak compressive strength of specimens. However, the positive effect of different side lengths of steel tube was not remarkable, even if the side length of the steel tube was doubled. This phenomenon showed that the increasing cross section area of concrete-filled steel tube played a trivial role in improving the axial strength of the composite columns. Different from the minor effect of side length, the increasing thickness of steel tube also can lead to a relative improvement on the non-linear slopes of these curves. This is because the sufficient confinement effect of steel tube can prevent the lateral expansion of inner concrete. Consequently, the concrete-filled steel tube form showed an enhancement in the compressive strength. After reaching peak strength, a dramatic drop can be seen from all specimen curves, and the specimens lost their workability. Due to the breakage of FRP bars, a gradual descending period can be seen in this stage, especially the specimens with stronger reinforcement. One note that the specimen of AL1T5-50 was not provided, due to the unexpected failure of LVDTs.

The effect of different FRP stirrup spacings

Figure 6 shows the early stage of hoop strain-axial strain curves of FRP stirrups measured from the strain gauges, that reflects the localized hoop strain-axial strain behavior of FRP stirrups at the initial ascending period. It is clear that the specimens with narrow FRP stirrup spacings presented small hoop at the same axial strain. This phenomenon proved the positive effect of the reinforcement of FRP stirrup, which was also consistent with the above discussions. One note that the representative curves of two groups, including AL0 and AL1T2.5, were discussed in this part. Since the decreasing FRP stirrup spacings can exhibit the improvement on all specimens, the other two groups were not described specifically.

The effect of different thickness of steel tube

In order to analyse to the effects of different thickness of steel tube, the hoop strain-axial strain curves of AL1T2.5 and AL1T5 were displayed in **Figure 7**. Similar with the effect of FRP stirrups, thinner steel tube showed large hoop strain under the same axial strain, even if a relatively slow slope can be seen at the beginning. On the other hand, it can be seen that the curves of specimens with thicker steel tube had a gentle slope, testifying the sufficient confinement effect can prevent the lateral expansion of inner concrete. Therefore, increasing the thickness of steel tube not only can play the positive role to the compressive behaviour of concrete-filled steel tube structure, but also can reflect the improvement to the composite columns.

The effect of different side lengths of steel tube

The hoop strain-axial strain curves of specimens with different side lengths of steel tube were showed in **Figure 8** for comparing. A minor difference of hoop strain can be seen, when the specimens with different side lengths of steel tube were at the same axial strain. This condition also can be proved by the above axial strength-strain curves, that the increasing side lengths of steel tube hardly exhibit positive effect on the specimens. Meanwhile, since the hoop strains, measured by strain gauges, were partial stains of steel tubes, the size effect of steel tube was barely reflected.

a) The group of AL1T2.5

b) The group of AL2T2.5

Figure 8: The hoop strain-axial strain curves of steel tube.

CONCLUSION

A novel sea-sand concrete column that was hybrid reinforced with FRP bars and steel tubes is proposed in this paper. Meanwhile, this paper examines the axial compression behavior of this composite structure and studies the impact of three variables: the presence of steel tubes, their side lengths, and their thicknesses. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results and the relative discussions:

- The failure mode of all specimens is dominated by the cracking of seawater sea sand concrete and the fracturing of some FRP bars. Due to the mechanical properties of FRP bars and seawater sea sand concrete, the specimens exhibit a brittle failure pattern.
- The decreasing of FRP stirrup spacings and the increasing thickness of steel tube perform positive effects on the bearing capacity of specimens, which are mainly reflected on the non-linear ascending period of the axial stress-axial strain curves.
- The positive effect of varying the side lengths of the steel tube was not significant, even if the side length is doubled. This suggests that increasing the cross-sectional area of the concrete-filled steel tube have little effect on enhancing the axial strength of the composite columns.
- The composite structure of FRP bars reinforced sea-sand concrete encased square steel tube columns can offer alternative choice for the construction of marine engineering, and this paper can provide a foundation for future researches on this type of structure.

CITATIONS

- Ahmed, A., Guo, S., Zhang, Z., Shi, C., & Zhu, D. (2020). A review on durability of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) bars reinforced seawater sea sand concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 256, 119484. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.119484>
- An, Y.-F., & Han, L.-H. (2014). Behaviour of concrete-encased CFST columns under combined compression and bending. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 101, 314-330. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2014.06.002>
- Cadenazzi, T., Nolan, S., Mazzocchi, G., Stringer, Z., & Nanni, A. (2020). Bridge Case Study: What a Contractor Needs to Know on an FRP Reinforcement Project. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 24(2), 05020001. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0000998
- Dong, Z., Wu, G., Zhao, X.-L., Zhu, H., & Lian, J.-L. (2018). Durability test on the flexural performance of seawater sea-sand concrete beams completely reinforced with FRP bars. *Construction and Building Materials*, 192, 671-682. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.10.166>
- Dong, Z., Wu, G., Zhao, X.-L., Zhu, H., Wei, Y., & Yan, Z. (2020). Mechanical properties of discrete BFRP needles reinforced seawater sea-sand concrete-filled GFRP tubular stub columns. *Construction and Building Materials*, 244, 118330.

Dundu, M. (2012). Compressive strength of circular concrete filled steel tube columns. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 56, 62-70. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2012.03.008>

Ekmekyapar, T., & Al-Eliwi, B. J. M. (2016). Experimental behaviour of circular concrete filled steel tube columns and design specifications. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 105, 220-230. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2016.04.004>

Guo, M., Hu, B., Xing, F., Zhou, X., Sun, M., Sui, L., & Zhou, Y. (2020). Characterization of the mechanical properties of eco-friendly concrete made with untreated sea sand and seawater based on statistical analysis. *Construction and Building Materials*, 234, 117339. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.117339>

Guo, X., Xiong, C., Jin, Z., & Pang, B. (2022). A review on mechanical properties of FRP bars subjected to seawater sea sand concrete environmental effects. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 58, 105038. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2022.105038>

Han, L.-H., & An, Y.-F. (2014). Performance of concrete-encased CFST stub columns under axial compression. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 93, 62-76. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2013.10.019>

Hou, C., & Zhou, X.-G. (2022). Strength prediction of circular CFST columns through advanced machine learning methods. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 51, 104289. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2022.104289>

Hu, X., Xiao, J., Zhang, K., & Zhang, Q. (2022). The state-of-the-art study on durability of FRP reinforced concrete with seawater and sea sand. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 51, 104294. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2022.104294>

Lai, M. H., & Ho, J. C. M. (2016). A theoretical axial stress-strain model for circular concrete-filled-steel-tube columns. *Engineering Structures*, 125, 124-143. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2016.06.048>

Lai, M. H., & Ho, J. C. M. (2017). An analysis-based model for axially loaded circular CFST columns. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 119, 770-781. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2017.07.024>

Lee, S.-H., Uy, B., Kim, S.-H., Choi, Y.-H., & Choi, S.-M. (2011). Behavior of high-strength circular concrete-filled steel tubular (CFST) column under eccentric loading. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 67(1), 1-13. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2010.07.003>

Li, P., Li, W., Yu, T., Qu, F., & Tam, V. W. Y. (2020). Investigation on early-age hydration, mechanical properties and microstructure of seawater sea sand cement mortar. *Construction and Building Materials*, 249, 118776. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.118776>

Li, Y., Teng, J., Zhao, X., & Raman, R. S. (2018). Theoretical model for seawater and sea sand concrete-filled circular FRP tubular stub columns under axial compression. *Engineering Structures*, 160, 71-84.

Nguyen, T.-T., Thai, H.-T., Ngo, T., Uy, B., & Li, D. (2021). Behaviour and design of high strength CFST columns with slender sections. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 182, 106645. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2021.106645>

Ozbakkaloglu, T., & Lim, J. C. (2013). Axial compressive behavior of FRP-confined concrete: Experimental test database and a new design-oriented model. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 55, 607-634. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2013.07.025>

Schneider Stephen, P. (1998). Axially Loaded Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes. *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 124(10), 1125-1138. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1998)124:10(1125)

Vincent, T., & Ozbakkaloglu, T. (2013). Influence of fiber orientation and specimen end condition on axial compressive behavior of FRP-confined concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 47, 814-826. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.05.085>

Xiao, J., Qiang, C., Nanni, A., & Zhang, K. (2017). Use of sea-sand and seawater in concrete construction: Current status and future opportunities. *Construction and Building Materials*, 155, 1101-1111. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.08.130>

Xie, J., Li, Y., Lu, Z., Fan, Z., Li, J., & Li, S. (2022). Effects of Immersion in Water, Alkaline Solution, and Seawater on the Shear Performance of Basalt FRP Bars in Seawater–Sea Sand Concrete. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 26(2), 04021071. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CC.1943-5614.0001184

Xiong, Z., Lin, L., Qiao, S., Li, L., Li, Y., He, S., . . . Chen, Y. (2022). Axial performance of seawater sea-sand concrete columns reinforced with basalt fibre-reinforced polymer bars under concentric

compressive load. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 47, 103828.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.103828>

Xiong, Z., Zeng, Y., Li, L. G., Kwan, A. K. H., & He, S. H. (2021). Experimental study on the effects of glass fibres and expansive agent on the bond behaviour of glass/basalt FRP bars in seawater sea-sand concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 274, 122100.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.122100>

Zeng, J.-J., Duan, Z.-J., Gao, W.-Y., Bai, Y.-L., & Ouyang, L.-J. (2020). Compressive behavior of FRP-wrapped seawater sea-sand concrete with a square cross-section. *Construction and Building Materials*, 262, 120881. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.120881>

Zeng, J.-J., Zheng, Y.-W., Liu, F., Guo, Y.-C., & Hou, C. (2021). Behavior of FRP Ring-Confined CFST columns under axial compression. *Composite Structures*, 257, 113166.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.113166>

Zhang, K., Zhang, Q., & Xiao, J. (2022). Durability of FRP bars and FRP bar reinforced seawater sea sand concrete structures in marine environments. *Construction and Building Materials*, 350, 128898.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.128898>

Zhang, Y., Wei, Y., Bai, J., Wu, G., & Dong, Z. (2020). A novel seawater and sea sand concrete filled FRP-carbon steel composite tube column: Concept and behaviour. *Composite Structures*, 246, 112421.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112421>

Zhao, Y., Hu, X., Shi, C., Zhang, Z., & Zhu, D. (2021). A review on seawater sea-sand concrete: Mixture proportion, hydration, microstructure and properties. *Construction and Building Materials*, 295, 123602. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.123602>

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request